

Office lighting

When research meets design

... and a new story begins

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"In an ideal world there [...] would be a smooth and obvious transfer of knowledge from lighting research to lighting design.

Researchers would be the producers of knowledge and understanding. Designers would be the consumers of that knowledge.

But this is not an ideal world. [...] anyone examining current lighting practice might suspect that lighting researchers and lighting designers inhabit different planets." (Boyce 1987)

If we know what living conditions are best for living creatures, why do we not design living and working spaces accordingly? Researchers refer to this approach as evidence-based design, that is to say, design based on proven scientific facts. That applies as much to a henhouse as to office environments

Aim

A review of the growing body of literature on architectural lighting reveals that much research has been conducted and published specifically for office lighting. However, little published work has been found to show that this research is making any significant contribution in the design of office lighting. The aim is to propose a framework consisting of well-researched characteristics, which can be used in the design of good quality office lighting. The characteristics listed in this framework are based on literature reviews, practical experience and common sense. The proposed framework does not attempt to provide taxonomies for office

might influence the thought process and suggest a new design approach. Consensus lighting, on the other hand, appears to have little to do with creativity. Instead, it is governed by the recommendations and procedures resulting from the consensus of lighting experts in a committee. The suggested lighting procedures can be applied by almost anyone with basic lighting knowledge. Lighting solutions based on consensus have been found reasonable for the type of application specified. But rarely does such lighting design evoke excitement in the designer or user, nor will it be influenced by research activity.

The second issue is the complexities posed by human visual and

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with the solar day and decrements in physiological functions, neuro-behavioural performance, and sleep usually occur (Brainard, Rollag et al. 1997). The dynamic quality of daylight has proven effects on human performance, triggering and reinforcing the body's natural biological rhythms; however, natural light can quickly become too much of a good thing with brightness levels that far exceed current recommendations particularly for VDT environments (Miller 2001). Emotional conditions influence perception: an imbalance between the sympathetic and the parasympathetic nervous systems could result in the misinterpretation of perceptual clues and ineffectiveness of the lighting system

Daytime activity curve according to Simeonova (2004).

lighting; it only provides perspectives and themes for analysis, and conceptual guidance for design.

Issues

In evaluating office lighting as a convenient context for observations about the lack of knowledge transfer from the lighting research community into the lighting design community several fundamental issues have been identified. The first issue as pointed by Boyce (1987) is the need for a classification for office lighting design that goes beyond designer lighting or consensus lighting. Designer lighting is the creation of an individual who creates a design based on personal experience and knowledge, often gained through a background in theatre lighting, which has provided expertise in painting with light. Research plays little or no role in the thought process as the designer is confident in his/her ability, creativity, and judgement, and seldom requires inspiration from research results. On rare occasions, research

non-visual systems on office workers' health and productivity. Over the course of the past two decades, new technologies, demographic trends, and ways of working in the corporate world have placed enormous demands on the human visual system. Besides tasks like reading printed matter, analysing figures on a VDT monitor, typing from reference documents and editing letters on a computer screen, a typical corporate office environment involves functions such as scanning colleagues' facial expressions and body language to assess the true meaning behind the words (Miller 2001). The non-visual systems consist of the circadian system for photo-biological health, and the perceptual system for emotional health. Light is the main input for synchronizing our biological clock to the solar [24-hour] day: if we are not exposed to a sufficient amount of light of the right spectrum for a sufficient amount of time and at the right timing, our biological clock becomes desynchronised

(Simeonova 2004). Stimulation is a psychological need that can be met by appropriate lighting; a stimulating environment can increase the satisfaction of performing boring tasks by increasing attentiveness, reducing fatigue, altering perceptions of time, and promoting positive moods by providing interest (Winchip 2005). However, the complexity of the perceptual system is not completely understood as it spurs from the great variability in human response (Boyce 2003).

The third issue as pointed by Willey (2006) is the need for a broader context of sustainable lighting, which embraces seizing the opportunity to enhance the quality of lit environments experienced by office workers. A growing concern in the building industry is the environmental impacts of energy consumption combined with the focus towards downsizing of financial and ecological costs of electrical usage for lighting in offices. The key message for lighting provided by the European Green Building pro-

gramme is that lighting has a substantial impact on the energy consumption in non-residential buildings, accounting for up to one third of the electricity used in some office buildings. All this has led to the building industry identifying sustainability only in the limited and readily quantifiable sense associated with aspects such as energy efficiency and the consumption of material resources. This industry bias is also reflected in the LEED certification system, as it does not spend a lot of time on lighting (Fehrenbacher 2006). The LEED-H covers lighting in this one sentence: "If you utilize energy efficient fixtures OR employ an Energy Star advanced lighting package, you can earn LEED points [...]."

Methodology

The proposed framework builds upon existing frameworks (Figueiro, Rea et al. 2002; Figueiro 2003; Simeonova 2004; Dugar 2009) for outlining an integrated set of well-researched characteristics that can be applied in the design of good quality office lighting. The goal is to find a universal solution that meets all the three fundamental issues identified in office lighting: transcend the parochial classifications of designer and consensus lighting; satisfy the needs of human visual and non-visual systems; and accrue points for sustainable lighting in its pristine sense. The framework utilizes the three universally accepted fundamental aspects of architectural lighting in their most simplistic form: the aesthetic, ergonomic, and logistic applications of design. The aesthetic aspect encompasses the general attractiveness of the lighting, while assessing the right kind of emotions it evokes. The ergonomic aspect encompasses the functional needs of the project for better visibility, while assessing comfort and wellbeing. The logistic aspect ensures that light and consequent energy is not wasted by over-illumination, either by illuminating vacant spaces unnecessarily or by providing more light than needed for the aesthetics or the task.

Aesthetic applications

The aesthetic applications of this framework are generally related to

sensations, involving pure emotions as opposed to pure intellectuality. The aesthetic experience of a space, being directly related to the perceptual system, is unpredictable due to the subjective preferences between, and within, individuals (Geyer 1983; Simeonova 2004). However, a universal observation is that lighting rooted in nature leads people to experience a feeling of wellbeing: uniform lighting patterns are viewed as monotonous and boring; varying light levels, using non-uniform lighting patterns at low illumination levels, and having windows to natural views are viewed as stimulating in office environments (Wilson 1999; Simeonova 2004; Winchip 2005). Even the concept and practice of sustainable lighting suggests a return to natural lighting and more natural environments with greater sensory stimulation and experiential richness (Willey 2006). Some research has found a connection between mood, gender, quantity of light, and the spectral distribution of a light source: although office lighting affects mood differently in men and women, warm light generated positive moods for both genders (Knez 1997; Knez 2001). The characteristics catering to the aesthetic applications for office lighting include:

⇒ Quantity: The quantity of light during the entire course of a working day should reflect the characteristics of daylight, besides sufficing minimum visual requirements to ensure that lighting is aesthetically pleasing. Preset scenes that provide bright light during the morning, with gradual decrease and increase as the day progresses could be set in accordance with the lighting algorithm.
 ⇒ Spectrum: daylight is perceived as white, but it contains all wavelengths and thus a simultaneous mix of warm and cool light (in accordance with the lighting algorithm). Saturated coloured light without white light has a tendency to produce colour washed shadows that appear unnatural, and hence should only be used for special effects with short exposure. All task-related applications requiring the use of coloured light should be in conjunction with white light to appear natural and aesthetically pleasing.

⇒ Timing: Introducing the time factor through perceptual constancies and adaptation can simultaneously satisfy the visual and non-visual systems. The passage of time can be depicted by a continuous and gradual transition from one lighting scene or emotion to another providing enough time for the individual to perceive and adapt, while avoiding any abrupt changes.
 ⇒ Duration: The duration of each lighting scene should be long enough to activate the right kind of emotion or mood required by the individual. For every change in a lighting scene, the new light settings should present hints of familiarity to help with the transition.
 ⇒ Spatial Distribution: In nature, the position of the sun as a light source anchors the composition of light and shadows to provide spatial orientation. In office lighting, although viewing points may differ, the logical pattern of light and shadows should reflect the quality of light we know from nature and preserve spatial orientation. The success of the skilful application of healthy lighting depends on the presence of abstract images of nature such as colour, texture, shapes and symbols.

Ergonomic applications

The ergonomic applications of this framework incorporate design factors intended to maximise productivity by minimising operator fatigue and discomfort. Visual comfort has a direct effect on the performance of task and productivity (Boyce, Veitch et al. 2004). Individuals need varying quantities and spectrums of light, depending upon age, gender and type of work: sufficient light supports the efficient and accurate performance of tasks, whereas insufficient light negates it, thereby affecting productivity (DiLouie 2003); women's problem-solving skills decrease in warm light and increase under cool sources, while men's problem-solving skills increase in warm light compared to cool light (Knez 1997). However, the adaptation levels of individuals have to be taken into account, by providing transition space and time for individuals to adapt to new light levels or scenes (Benya, Heschong et al. 2003). Blue-rich ambient light

leads to smaller pupils, which in turn increase individuals' depth of field and visual acuity compared to blue deficient ambient light; this means that cool lighting is suitable for visual performance of tasks as it produces higher contrast (Navvab 2001; Powell and Weinberg 2002; Benya, Heschong et al. 2003). Additionally, as the biological effects of light are mediated by retinal photoreceptors, once the task in a space is defined, light that is biologically active should be provided where the eye is (Veitch 2003). The characteristics catering to the ergonomic aspects of office lighting include:
 ⇒ Quantity: Bright light exposure is required for both task performance and activation of the circadian system. On the other hand, brightness adaptation while moving from one task to another directly affects visual comfort. As excessive brightness or uneven distribution in the field of view can cause glare, the light levels provided in an office environment should be based on brightness adaptation under individual working conditions.
 ⇒ Spectrum: Blue-rich ambient light is an essential requirement for increased task performance and activation of the circadian system as it is responsive to the short wavelength portion. The morning boost and post-lunch dip of the lighting algorithm require bright light levels that cater to the 'blue-end' of the light spectrum.
 ⇒ Timing and Duration: In areas where natural lighting becomes a problem, dynamic electric lighting can phase-advance or phase-delay the biological clock, as well as ensure melatonin suppression by following the lighting algorithm.
 ⇒ Spatial Distribution: The distribution of light in a space, particularly the luminances on room surfaces, appears to be a major determinant on room satisfaction. Instead of providing a uniform blanket of light, intermittent bright and less bright areas could be provided for task and circulation areas respectively. Rather than providing increased illuminance throughout interiors, exposure to biologically active lighting can be increased by providing areas of higher illuminance where they will be frequently viewed.

Logistic applications

The logistic applications of this framework involve the planning, implementation, and coordination of office lighting. Chapter 27 of the IESNA Lighting Handbook describes energy management, aesthetics, and code compliance measures as the three major objectives for the use of lighting controls (Rea 2000). Lighting controls can form a core of the aesthetic and ergonomic applications of this framework in offices: by allowing a measure of control over the lighting, a relationship can be established between the light source and the individual (Powell and Weinberg 2002); individuals can create emotional appeal by changing lighting quality, mood, colour, and attitude depending upon their subjective needs (Rea 2000); this relationship in turn can have positive returns in morale and productivity (Miller 2001). Individuals place a high level of importance on being able to control lighting; certain individuals pro-actively use controls to set preferred conditions and not solely use controls in response to discomfort (Moore, Carter et al. 2002). Such fine-tuned lighting controls can in turn become an integral part of the healthy lighting system (Simeonova 2004). The European Green Light programme reports that energy savings between 30 to 50 per cent can be achieved in a normal office building by retrofitting existing fixtures with efficient ballasts, lamps, and reflectors; even larger savings may be gained through comprehensive redesigning of lighting and control systems. The characteristics catering to the logistic aspect of office lighting include:
 ⇒ Quantity and Spectrum: Office workers should be provided with individualised control over the lighting of their work areas. Switching, dimming, and preset controls should be used wherever applicable, with appropriate light sources and control gear to change the quantity and spectrum of light. Dimming controls give individuals the ability to raise or lower lighting levels, whereas with preset controls individuals can set or recall multiple moods or scenes.
 ⇒ Timing and Duration: Lighting systems with timers can be used to

set different moods or scenes according to the individuals' subjective requirements or match the dynamic qualities of daylight during the course of the day. Individuals can phase-advance their biological clock every morning in order to be synchronised to the solar day, or phase-delay it. Timers can also bring about energy savings by automatically switching-off light sources after all occupants vacate the building at the end of a working day.
 ⇒ Spatial Distribution: With a well laid-out and distributed lighting control plan the spatial distribution of light can be set to meet the visual and non-visual requirements of individuals, as well as prevent wastage of light. Locally available manual dimming and preset controls should be utilised wherever possible to improve the variable response of individuals towards lighting. Besides, the use of gobos and other optical techniques can provide views of abstracted images of nature within interior spaces.

In Conclusion

The proposed framework recognises and defines research needs in office lighting design, and develops solutions in response to those needs. The solutions provided by this framework could have greater opportunities for application in other areas of lighting design as well, such as hospitality and health care. "But with greater opportunities and knowledge comes increased responsibility" (Osterhaus and Dugar 2009); hence the appropriateness of each of the framework characteristics has to be clearly defined before applying them in the different areas. On a broader context, the development of such a framework can be considered as a first step in moving the whole lighting community – researchers, designers and manufacturers – onto the same planet!

References

⇒ Benya, J., L. Heschong, et al. (2003). Advanced Lighting Guidelines. White Salmon, WA, USA, New Buildings Institute Inc.
 ⇒ Boyce, P. R. (1987). Lighting Research and Lighting Design – Bridging the Gap. Lighting Design + Application.

New York, USA, IES. 17: 38-44.
 ⇒ Boyce, P. R. (2003). Human Factors in Lighting. New York, NY, USA, Taylor & Francis.
 ⇒ Boyce, P. R., J. A. Veitch, et al. (2004). Lighting Quality and Office Work: A Field Simulation Study. U. S. D. o. Energy, National Research Council, Canada: 167.
 ⇒ Brainard, G. C., M. D. Rollag, et al. (1997). "Photic Regulation of Melatonin in Humans: Ocular and Neural Signal Transduction." *Biological Rhythms* 12(6): 537-546.
 ⇒ DiLouie, C. (2003). "Lighting Strategies – New Study Explores Lighting & Productivity Link." *Buildings Magazine* December 2003. Retrieved 07 May, 2008, from <http://www.buildings.com/articles/detail.aspx?contentID=1710>.
 ⇒ Dugar, A. M. (2009). "Applications of lighting for visual and non-visual systems." *Lighting India* 4(2): 44-53.
 ⇒ Fehrenbacher, J. (2006) "Green Building 101: Environmentally Friendly Lighting." *Inhabitat – Green design will save the world*.
 ⇒ Figueiro, M. G. (2003). "Research Recap: Circadian Rhythm." *Lighting Design + Application (LD+A)* 33(2): 17-19.
 ⇒ Figueiro, M. G., M. S. Rea, et al. (2002). Daylight and Productivity – A Possible Link to Circadian Regulation. Light and Human Health: EPRI/LRO 5th International Lighting Research Symposium. Palo Alto, CA, USA, The Lighting Research Office of the Electric Power Research Institute: 185-193.
 ⇒ Geyer, R. L. (1983, November 1988). "Perception and the Aesthetic Experience." In *Search of the Aesthetic: A Study of Relevant Detail in Art* Retrieved 08 August, 2008, from <http://www.aestheticendeavors.com/articles/Perception.pdf>.
 ⇒ Knez, I. (1997). Changes in Females' and Males' Positive and Negative Moods as a Result of Variations in CCT, CRI and Illuminance Levels. *Right Light* 4.
 ⇒ Knez, I. (2001). "Effects of color of light on nonvisual psychological processes." *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 21: 201-208.
 ⇒ Miller, H. (2001). "Lighting in the Workplace." Retrieved September 2007, from http://www.hermanmiller.com.mx/pdf/wp_lighting_in_wkpl.pdf.
 ⇒ Moore, T., D. J. Carter, et al. (2002). "User attitudes toward occupant controlled office lighting." *Lighting Re-*

search and Technology 34(3): 207-216.
 ⇒ Navvab, M. (2001). Visual Performance Analysis of Office Occupants Working Under Realistic Luminous Environment Conditions. *Full Spectrum Solutions*.
 ⇒ Osterhaus, W. and A. M. Dugar (2009). The weight of research in disseminating light: Defining research in architectural lighting design education. *Professional Lighting Design Conference: 2nd Global Lighting Design Conference*. J. Ritter. Berlin, Germany, VIA-Verlag.
 ⇒ Powell, B. J. and L. Weinberg. (2002). "The Ergonomics of Light." *Buildings Magazine* October 2002. Retrieved 06 May, 2008, from <http://www.buildings.com/articles/detail.aspx?contentID=1070>.
 ⇒ Rea, M. S., Ed. (2000). The IESNA lighting handbook : reference & application. New York, USA, Illuminating Engineering Society of North America.
 ⇒ Simeonova, M. (2004). "Healthy Lighting for the Visual, Circadian and Perceptual Systems." *Business Briefing: Hospital Engineering & Facilities Management*: 99-102.
 ⇒ Veitch, J. A. (2003). "Principles of healthy lighting: a role for daylight". *International Daylighting RD+A 5* (March): 5-6.
 ⇒ Willey, H. (2006). "Sustainable Lighting and Sense-Rich Environments." *Journal of Light & Visual Environment* 30(2): 68-73.
 ⇒ Wilson, M. (1999). *Visual Comfort and Energy Saving*, University of North London: 11.
 ⇒ Winchip, S. M. (2005). *Designing a Quality Lighting Environment*. New York, USA, Fairchild Publications.